

Concept of disrespectful and abusive care during childbirth in high income countries: A systematic scoping review protocol.

AUTHORS' FULL NAME AND ACADEMIC DEGREES (alphabetic order)

Pauline Blanc-Petitjean, RM, PhD,¹

Marianne Jacques, RM, MSc,²

Camille Le Ray, MD, PhD,^{2,3}

AUTHOR'S AFFILIATIONS

¹ University Rennes, CHU Rennes, INSERM, EHESP, IRSET (Institut de recherche en santé, environnement et travail), UMR 1085, Rennes, France

² Université Paris Cité, Inserm U1153, Centre for Research in Epidemiology and Statistics (CRESS), Obstetric, Perinatal, Paediatric Life Course Epidemiology Research Team (OPPaLE), Paris, France.

³ Maternité Port Royal, Hôpital Cochin Port Royal, Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris, Université Paris Cité, Paris, France.

E-MAIL ADDRESSES OF ALL CO-AUTHORS

Pauline Blanc-Petitjean: pauline.blanc-petitjean@inserm.fr

Marianne Jacques: marianne.jacques@inserm.fr

Camille Le Ray: camille.le-ray@aphp.fr

INTRODUCTION

The medicalization of childbirth constitutes a major advance for the health of women and children by enabling the decrease of maternal and infant mortality rates as well as complications due to pregnancy and childbirth. Thus, in recent decades, intensive medical monitoring of pregnancies and institutional delivery has been promoted through community mobilization, education, financial incentives, or policy measures, resulting in a net improvement in hospital delivery rates.¹ However, accounts of women's negative experiences of medical care during intrapartum care have received increasing attention in recent years in all regions of the world.² While disrespectful and abusive treatment of women may occur throughout pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period, women are particularly vulnerable during childbirth. Supported by a WHO statement in 2014,¹ the issue of disrespect and abuse during intrapartum care generated new research across different continents, collective awareness, and a growing number of interventions especially in low- and middle-income countries.²⁻⁷ However, an overview of the literature identifies a wide variety of terminologies used that sometimes refer to very different concepts, especially depending on whether one is interested in low- and middle-income countries or high-income countries.⁸ The choice of terms used, generally made up of "abuse", "mistreatment" and "disrespect", has major implications for the understanding that will be given to this serious issue. For example, some authors advocate the use of the term "obstetric violence", initially defined by the Organic Law of Venezuela, considering the gender-based violence dimension to be essential.⁹ A synthesis of this phenomenon on an international scale is underway¹⁰ but the very specific medical, social, and legal expectations regarding birth in high-income countries require that a more comprehensive synthesis be conducted in this context.¹¹ Given the diversity of concepts, terminologies, and measures of disrespectful and abusive care during childbirth, their evaluation mainly in the context of low- and middle-income

countries, and the growing interest in this hot topic in the literature, we considered that performing a scoping review focused on high-income countries was warranted.

The main objective of this scoping review will be to analyse the concept of disrespectful and abusive care of women during childbirth in high income countries by focusing on the terminology used and the concepts it evaluates, and finally the gaps in the literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

General methodology

We will conduct a scoping review following the method proposed by the Johanna Briggs Institute¹² and reported the results according to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) guidelines¹³ (**Supplemental Table 1**).

Eligibility criteria

We will include original studies that reported qualitative or quantitative or mixed data on adverse experiences related to interactions with health care providers during labour, childbirth or postpartum reported by women who gave birth in health facilities in high-income countries defined as the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) members with high-income economy^{14,15} (**Supplemental Table 2**). Studies reporting negative or positive experiences of childbirth without making it clear whether or not this was related to a disorder of interaction with caregivers will be excluded. Studies that report on one or more behaviours that could be considered disrespectful but do not provide an overall terminology for the concept will be excluded.

Search strategy and information sources

We will search for study reports published from January 1, 2000 (period of emergence of the denunciation of disrespectful care during childbirth in Latin America) to January 1, 2023, in MEDLINE via PubMed, and Scopus electronic databases. The search strategy will combine groups of keywords pertaining to (i) disrespectful and abusive care, (ii) pregnancy and childbirth with (iii) exclusion of keywords related to substance abuse, child abuse or domestic violence and (iv) a geographical restriction to high-income countries excluding keywords

related to low- and middle-income countries adapted from search strategies published by the University Libraries Health Sciences Library¹⁶ in order to avoid missing publications of interest conducted in high-income countries that do not mention their location (**Supplemental Table 3**). No language restrictions will be applied.

Two review authors (MJ and PBP) will exclude independently clearly ineligible studies based on their titles and abstracts using the online software platform Covidence®. Then they independently will evaluate the full text of relevant articles for inclusion using the predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Discrepancies will be resolved with a discussion among the review authors. Finally, one review author (MJ) will ensure literature saturation by searching the reference list of included studies, the list of articles citing them on PubMed and the individual studies included in systematic reviews, if relevant.

Data extraction

For included articles, the two review authors (MJ and PBP) will use an extraction form to independently report the collect data regarding the following characteristics:

- Study: title, year of publication, journal, author, field of study (qualitative / quantitative /mixed-methods);
- Participants: data collection timing regarding delivery, patient recruitment;
- Concept: terminology, dimensions assessed;
- Context: country, stage assessed (i.e. labour, delivery, postpartum);
- Measurement tool (for quantitative data): name of questionnaire, external/internal validation, number and nature of items assessed, prevalence.

Discrepancies between review authors will be discussed and solved by consensus or by soliciting a third review author (CLR).

Data synthesis

A synthesis of all the types of disrespectful and abusive care of the caregivers that can be negatively felt by the mother during pregnancy and childbirth and evoked in the literature will be performed. The terminology used in each article will be identified and the different dimensions of the concept associated with this terminology by the authors will be categorised according to the classification published by Bohren et al. (**Table 1**):²

- Physical abuse (use of force, physical restraint);
- Sexual abuse;
- Verbal abuse (threats, harsh language);
- Stigma and discrimination;
- Failure to meet professional standards of care (lack of informed consent and confidentiality, physical examinations and procedures, neglect and abandonment);
- Poor rapport between woman and providers (ineffective communication, lack of supportive care, loss of autonomy);
- Health system conditions and constraints (lack of resources, lack of policies, facility culture);
- Where appropriate, other categories that have been identified.

We will identify definitions that seem to be consensual and gaps in the concepts studied in the literature. The methods of data collection, the timing of collection after delivery, the measurement tools used (validated tools or ad hoc questions), and the reported prevalence of disrespectful and abusive care will be described (**Tables 2 and 3**).

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DECLARATIONS

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable

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TABLES

Table 1. Terminology and concepts

<i>Terminology</i> - authors	Concept	
	Use of force	Physical abuse
	Physical restraint	
	Sexual abuse	
	Harsh language	Verbal abuse
	Threats and blaming	
	Based on sociodemographic characteristics	Stigma and discrimination
	Based on medical conditions	
	Lack of informed consent	Failure to meet professional standards of care
	Lack of confidentiality	
	Procedures without pain management	
	Neglect and abandonment	Poor rapport between woman and providers
	Ineffective communication	
	Poor staff attitudes	
	Lack of supportive care	
	Loss of autonomy (treated as passive participant)	
	Loss of autonomy (denial of foods, fluids, mobility ...)	
	Detainment in facilities	Health system conditions and constraints
	Lack of resources	
	Lack of policies	
	Unfair fee	
	Other (clearly stated)	

Table 2. Synthesis of included studies

First author	Title	Journal	Year	Country	Language	Type of publication	Type of data	Sampling	Participants	Terminology

Table 3. Measurement tools

Questionnaire name	Validation / language or country	Number and nature of items	Timing of assessment	Developed / used by Author, Journal, Year

APPENDIX

Supplemental Table 1. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist.

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	Click here to enter text.
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	Click here to enter text.
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	Click here to enter text.
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	Click here to enter text.
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	Click here to enter text.
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	Click here to enter text.
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	Click here to enter text.
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	Click here to enter text.
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	Click here to enter text.
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	Click here to enter text.

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	Click here to enter text.
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	Click here to enter text.
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	Click here to enter text.
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	Click here to enter text.
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	Click here to enter text.
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	Click here to enter text.
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	Click here to enter text.
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	Click here to enter text.
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	Click here to enter text.
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	Click here to enter text.
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	Click here to enter text.
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	Click here to enter text.

JB: Joanna Briggs Institute; *PRISMA-ScR*: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews

* Where *sources of evidence* (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley and Levac and colleagues and the JBI guidance refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).

Supplemental Table 2. List of OECD member countries with ranked as high-income economies by the World Bank (alphabetic order)^{14,15}

Australia
Austria
Belgium
Canada
Chile
Czech Republic
Denmark
Estonia
Finland
France
Germany
Greece
Hungary
Iceland
Ireland
Israel
Italy
Japan
Korea
Latvia
Lithuania
Luxembourg
Netherlands
New Zealand
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Slovak Republic
Slovenia
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
United Kingdom
United States

Supplemental Table 3. Search boxes.

<p>Pubmed</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "abus*"[Title/Abstract] OR "birth experience" [Title/Abstract] OR "respectful maternity care" [Title/Abstract] OR "disrespect*"[Title/Abstract] OR "mistreat*"[Title/Abstract] OR "violence"[Title/Abstract] OR "inappropriate behavior"[Title/Abstract] 2. "Parturition" [MeSH Terms] OR "Pregnancy" [MeSH Terms] OR "childbirth"[Title/Abstract] OR "obstetric"[Title/Abstract] OR "Delivery, Obstetric" [MeSH Terms] OR "Labor, Obstetric" [MeSH Terms] 3. "drug*"[Title/Abstract] OR "therapy"[Title/Abstract] OR "cocaine"[Title/Abstract] OR "alcohol"[Title/Abstract] OR "substance*"[Title/Abstract] OR "treatment"[Title/Abstract] OR "child abuse"[Title/Abstract] OR "child maltreatment"[Title/Abstract] OR "childhood abuse"[Title/Abstract] OR "childhood neglect"[Title/Abstract] OR "family"[Title/Abstract] OR "domestic"[Title/Abstract] OR "partner violence"[Title/Abstract] 4. (Afghanistan[Title/Abstract] OR Albania[Title/Abstract] OR Algeria[Title/Abstract] OR "American Samoa"[Title/Abstract] OR Angola[Title/Abstract] OR Argentina[Title/Abstract] OR "Argentine Republic"[Title/Abstract] OR Armenia[Title/Abstract] OR Azerbaijan[Title/Abstract] OR Bangladesh[Title/Abstract] OR Belarus[Title/Abstract] OR Byelarus[Title/Abstract] OR Belorussia[Title/Abstract] OR Belize[Title/Abstract] OR Benin[Title/Abstract] OR Bhutan[Title/Abstract] OR Bolivia[Title/Abstract] OR Bosnia[Title/Abstract] OR Botswana[Title/Abstract] OR Brazil[Title/Abstract] OR Bulgaria[Title/Abstract] OR Burma[Title/Abstract] OR "Burkina Faso"[Title/Abstract] OR Burundi[Title/Abstract] OR "Cabo Verde"[Title/Abstract] OR "Cape verde"[Title/Abstract] OR Cambodia[Title/Abstract] OR Cameroon[Title/Abstract] OR "Central African Republic"[Title/Abstract] OR Chad[Title/Abstract] OR China[Title/Abstract] OR Colombia[Title/Abstract] OR Comoros[Title/Abstract] OR Comores[Title/Abstract] OR Comoro[Title/Abstract] OR Congo[Title/Abstract] OR "Costa Rica"[Title/Abstract] OR "Côte d'Ivoire"[Title/Abstract] OR Cuba[Title/Abstract] OR Djibouti[Title/Abstract] OR Dominica[Title/Abstract] OR "Dominican Republic"[Title/Abstract] OR Ecuador[Title/Abstract] OR Egypt[Title/Abstract] OR "El Salvador"[Title/Abstract] OR Eritrea[Title/Abstract] OR Ethiopia[Title/Abstract] OR Fiji[Title/Abstract] OR Gabon[Title/Abstract] OR Gambia[Title/Abstract] OR Gaza[Title/Abstract] OR "Georgia Republic"[Title/Abstract] OR Georgian[Title/Abstract] OR Ghana[Title/Abstract] OR Grenada[Title/Abstract] OR Grenadines[Title/Abstract] OR Guatemala[Title/Abstract] OR Guinea[Title/Abstract] OR "Guinea Bissau"[Title/Abstract] OR Guyana[Title/Abstract] OR Haiti[Title/Abstract] OR Herzegovina[Title/Abstract] OR Hercegovina[Title/Abstract] OR Honduras[Title/Abstract] OR India[Title/Abstract] OR Indonesia[Title/Abstract] OR Iran[Title/Abstract] OR Iraq[Title/Abstract] OR Jamaica[Title/Abstract] OR Jordan[Title/Abstract] OR Kazakhstan[Title/Abstract] OR Kenya[Title/Abstract] OR Kiribati[Title/Abstract] OR "North Korea"[Title/Abstract] OR Kosovo[Title/Abstract] OR Kyrgyz[Title/Abstract] OR Kirghizia[Title/Abstract] OR Kirghiz[Title/Abstract] OR Kirgizstan[Title/Abstract] OR Kyrgyzstan[Title/Abstract] OR "Lao PDR"[Title/Abstract] OR Laos[Title/Abstract] OR Lebanon[Title/Abstract] OR Lesotho[Title/Abstract] OR Liberia[Title/Abstract] OR Libya[Title/Abstract] OR Macedonia[Title/Abstract] OR Madagascar[Title/Abstract] OR Malawi[Title/Abstract] OR Malay[Title/Abstract] OR Malaya[Title/Abstract] OR Malaysia[Title/Abstract] OR Maldives[Title/Abstract] OR Mali[Title/Abstract] OR "Marshall Islands"[Title/Abstract] OR Mauritania[Title/Abstract] OR Mauritius[Title/Abstract] OR Mexico[Title/Abstract] OR Micronesia[Title/Abstract] OR
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Moldova[Title/Abstract] OR Mongolia[Title/Abstract] OR Montenegro[Title/Abstract] OR Morocco[Title/Abstract] OR Mozambique[Title/Abstract] OR Myanmar[Title/Abstract] OR Namibia[Title/Abstract] OR Nauru[Title/Abstract] OR Nepal[Title/Abstract] OR Nicaragua[Title/Abstract] OR Niger[Title/Abstract] OR Nigeria [Title/Abstract] OR Pakistan [Title/Abstract] OR Palau[Title/Abstract] OR Panama[Title/Abstract] OR "Papua New Guinea"[Title/Abstract] OR Paraguay[Title/Abstract] OR Peru [Title/Abstract] OR Philippines[Title/Abstract] OR Phillippines[Title/Abstract] OR Philipines[Title/Abstract] OR Phillipines[Title/Abstract] OR Principe[Title/Abstract] OR Romania[Title/Abstract] OR Rwanda[Title/Abstract] OR Ruanda[Title/Abstract] OR Samoa[Title/Abstract] OR "Sao Tome"[Title/Abstract] OR Senegal[Title/Abstract] OR Serbia[Title/Abstract] OR "Sierra Leone"[Title/Abstract] OR "Solomon Islands"[Title/Abstract] OR Somalia[Title/Abstract] OR "South Africa"[Title/Abstract] OR "South Sudan"[Title/Abstract] OR "Sri Lanka"[Title/Abstract] OR "St Lucia"[Title/Abstract] OR "St Vincent"[Title/Abstract] OR Sudan[Title/Abstract] OR Surinam[Title/Abstract] OR Suriname[Title/Abstract] OR Swaziland[Title/Abstract] OR Syria[Title/Abstract] OR "Syrian Arab Republic"[Title/Abstract] OR Tajikistan[Title/Abstract] OR Tadhikistan[Title/Abstract] OR Tadjikistan[Title/Abstract] OR Tadhik[Title/Abstract] OR Tanzania[Title/Abstract] OR Thailand[Title/Abstract] OR Timor[Title/Abstract] OR Togo[Title/Abstract] OR Tonga[Title/Abstract] OR Tunisia[Title/Abstract] OR Turkey[Title/Abstract] OR Turkmen[Title/Abstract] OR Turkmenistan[Title/Abstract] OR Tuvalu[Title/Abstract] OR Uganda[Title/Abstract] OR Ukraine[Title/Abstract] OR Uzbek[Title/Abstract] OR Uzbekistan[Title/Abstract] OR Vanuatu[Title/Abstract] OR Venezuela[Title/Abstract] OR Vietnam[Title/Abstract] OR "West Bank"[Title/Abstract] OR Yemen[Title/Abstract] OR Zambia[Title/Abstract] OR Zimbabwe[Title/Abstract] OR "Deprived Countries"[Title/Abstract] OR "Deprived Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Developing Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Developing Econom*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Developing Nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Developing Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Developing World"[Title/Abstract] OR "LAMI Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Less Developed Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Less Developed Economies"[Title/Abstract] OR "Less Developed Nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Less Developed World"[Title/Abstract] OR "Lesser Developed Countries"[Title/Abstract] OR "Lesser Developed Nations"[Title/Abstract] OR "LMIC*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low GDP"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low GNP"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low Gross Domestic"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low Gross National"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low Income"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low-Income"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low Income Econom*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low Income Nations"[Title/Abstract] OR "Low Income Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Lower GDP"[Title/Abstract] OR "lower gross domestic"[Title/Abstract] OR "Lower Income Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Lower Income Nations"[Title/Abstract] OR "Lower Income Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Middle Income Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Middle Income Economies"[Title/Abstract] OR "Middle Income Nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Middle Income Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poor Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poor Econom*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poor Nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poor Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "poor world"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poorer Countries"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poorer Econom*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poorer Nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Poorer Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Third World"[Title/Abstract] OR "Transitional Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Transitional Econom*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Under Developed Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "under developed nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Under Developed World"[Title/Abstract] OR "Under Served

	<p>Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Underdeveloped Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "underdeveloped econom*"[Title/Abstract] OR "underdeveloped nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "underdeveloped population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Underdeveloped World"[Title/Abstract] OR "Underserved Countr*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Underserved Nation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Underserved Population*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Arab World"[Title/Abstract])</p> <p>1 AND 2 NOT 3 NOT 4 Human species restriction From 2000</p>
<p>Scopus</p>	<p>1. "abuse during pregnancy" OR "abuse during childbirth" OR "respectful maternity care" OR "birth experience" OR "disrespect during childbirth" OR "mistreatment during childbirth" OR "obstetrical violence" OR "violence obstétricales" OR "violence obstétrica" OR "violence obstétrica" OR "violence ostetrica"</p> <p>2. drug OR therapy OR cocaine OR alcohol OR substance OR treatment OR "child abuse" OR "child maltreatment" OR "childhood abuse" OR "childhood neglect" OR "family" OR "domestic" OR "partner violence"</p> <p>3. (Afghanistan OR Albania OR Algeria OR "American Samoa" OR Angola OR Argentina OR Armenia OR Azerbaijan OR Bangladesh OR Belarus OR Byelarus OR Belorussia OR Belize OR Benin OR Bhutan OR Bolivia OR Bosnia OR Botswana OR Brazil OR Bulgaria OR Burma OR "Burkina Faso" OR Burundi OR "Cabo Verde" OR "Cape verde" OR Cambodia OR Cameroon OR "Central African Republic" OR Chad OR China OR Colombia OR Comoros OR Comores OR Comoro OR Congo OR "Costa Rica" OR "Côte d'Ivoire" OR Cuba OR Djibouti OR Dominica OR "Dominican Republic" OR Ecuador OR Egypt OR "El Salvador" OR Eritrea OR Ethiopia OR Fiji OR Gabon OR Gambia OR Gaza OR "Georgia Republic" OR Georgian OR Ghana OR Grenada OR Grenadines OR Guatemala OR Guinea OR "Guinea Bissau" OR Guyana OR Haiti OR Herzegovina OR Hercegovina OR Honduras OR India OR Indonesia OR Iran OR Iraq OR Jamaica OR Jordan OR Kazakhstan OR Kenya OR Kiribati OR "North Korea" OR Kosovo OR Kyrgyz OR Kirghizia OR Kirghiz OR Kirgizstan OR Kyrgyzstan OR "Lao PDR" OR Laos OR Lebanon OR Lesotho OR Liberia OR Libya OR Macedonia OR Madagascar OR Malawi OR Malay OR Malaya OR Malaysia OR Maldives OR Mali OR "Marshall Islands" OR Mauritania OR Mauritius OR Mexico OR Micronesia OR Moldova OR Mongolia OR Montenegro OR Morocco OR Mozambique OR Myanmar OR Namibia OR Nauru OR Nepal OR Nicaragua OR Niger OR Nigeria OR Pakistan OR Palau OR Panama OR "Papua New Guinea" OR Paraguay OR Peru OR Philippines OR Phillippines OR Philipines OR Phillipines OR Principe OR Romania OR Rwanda OR Ruanda OR Samoa OR "Sao Tome" OR Senegal OR Serbia OR "Sierra Leone" OR "Solomon Islands" OR Somalia OR "South Africa" OR "South Sudan" OR "Sri Lanka" OR "St Lucia" OR "St Vincent" OR Sudan OR Surinam OR Suriname OR Swaziland OR Syria OR "Syrian Arab Republic" OR Tajikistan OR Tadhikistan OR Tadjikistan OR Tadhik OR Tanzania OR Thailand OR Timor OR Togo OR Tonga OR Tunisia OR Turkey OR Turkmen OR Turkmenistan OR Tuvalu OR Uganda OR Ukraine OR Uzbek OR Uzbekistan OR Vanuatu OR Venezuela OR Vietnam OR "West Bank" OR Yemen OR Zambia OR Zimbabwe OR "Deprived Countries" OR "Deprived Population" OR "Developing Country" OR "Developing Economy" OR "Developing Nation" OR "Developing Population" OR "Developing World" OR "LAMI Country" OR "Less</p>

Developed Country" OR "Less Developed Economies" OR "Less Developed Nation" OR "Less Developed World" OR "Lesser Developed Countries" OR "Lesser Developed Nations" OR "LMIC" OR "Low GDP" OR "Low GNP" OR "Low Gross Domestic" OR "Low Gross National" OR "Low Income" OR "Low-Income" OR "Low Income Economy" OR "Low Income Nation" OR "Low Income Population" OR "Lower GDP" OR "lower gross domestic" OR "Lower Income Countries" OR "Lower Income Nation" OR "Lower Income Population" OR "Middle Income Countries" OR "Middle Income Economies" OR "Middle Income Nation" OR "Middle Income Population" OR "Poor Countries" OR "Poor Economies" OR "Poor Nations" OR "Poor Population" OR "poor world" OR "Poorer Countries" OR "Poorer Economies" OR "Poorer Nation" OR "Poorer Population" OR "Third World" OR "Transitional Country" OR "Transitional Economy" OR "Under Developed Countries" OR "under developed nations" OR "Under Developed World" OR "Under Served Population" OR "Underdeveloped Country" OR "underdeveloped economy" OR "underdeveloped nation" OR "underdeveloped population" OR "Underdeveloped World" OR "Underserved Countries" OR "Underserved Nation" OR "Underserved Population" OR "Arab World")

4. > 1999

5. < 2024

ALL 1 AND NOT 2 AND NOT 3 AND PUBYEAR 4 AND PUBYEAR 5